

ANALYSIS ON DATA WITH TRIALINDEX 1-10

Number of trials per stimulus mode					
	0	100	140	180	Total
None	16	-	-	-	16
AudioOnly	-	20	30	22	72
VisualsOnly	-	30	24	28	82
Both	-	23	31	25	79
Total	16	73	85	75	249

Stimuli type and performance

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variable: correctNormalized

ANOVA correctNormalized~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
2.047	0.108	

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasStimulusTrial				
mean	Has-No	t	p	
0.9998344	0.9986727	0.066969	0.9472	

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasVisualTrial				
mean	Has-No	t	p	
0.9955622	1.0074880	-0.77819	0.4377	

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasAudioTrial				
mean	Has-No	t	p	
1.0126879	0.9797089	2.4321	0.01577	

Stimuli tempo and performance

Parameter: tempo | Variable: correctNormalized | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo		
F	p	
0.325	0.808	

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]		
F	p	
0.862	0.427	

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
0.175	0.84	

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
0.143	0.867	

Stimuli type and time estimation

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception)

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
0.569	0.636	

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasStimulusTrial				
mean	Has-No	t	p	
0.0120830	0.0290069	-0.5091	0.6118	

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasVisualTrial				
mean	Has-No	t	p	
0.0117994	0.0166969	-0.23071	0.8176	

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasAudioTrial				
mean	Has-No	t	p	
0.0205346	0.0035358	0.79259	0.4283	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
0.569	0.636	

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasStimulusTrial				
mean	Has-No	t	p	
0.2202785	0.2131982	0.31973	0.7498	

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasVisualTrial				
mean	Has-No	t	p	
0.2206991	0.2178860	0.19309	0.8469	

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasAudioTrial				
mean	Has-No	t	p	
0.2190183	0.2204408	-0.095811	0.9237	

Stimuli tempo and time estimation

Parameter: tempo | Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception) | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo		
F	p	
1.194	0.312	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]		
F	p	
0.229	0.796	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
0.444	0.643	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
1.691	0.191	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo		
F	p	
1.178	0.319	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]		
F	p	
0.902	0.411	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
2.056	0.135	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
1.146	0.323	

Stimuli type and time judgment

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variable: reportedSpeedPerception

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~classes			
chi-2	df	p	
5.6923	3	0.1276	

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasStimulusTrial				
W	p			
2286.5	0.1129			
mean Has	mean Not			
3.51073	3.0625			

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasAudioTrial				
W	p			
8209	0.127			
mean Has	mean Not			
3.562914	3.357143			

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasVisualTrial				
W	p			
7722	0.2193			
mean Has	mean Not			
3.540373	3.375			

Stimuli tempo and time judgment

Parameter: tempo | Variable: reportedSpeedPerception | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo			
chi-2	df	p	
4.9341	3	0.1767	

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]			
chi-2	df	p	
4.0273	2	0.1335	

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]			
chi-2	df	p	
3.2024	2	0.2017	

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterBOTH]			
chi-2	df	p	
4.0016	2	0.1352	

Correlations time judgment - estimation - performance

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), reportedSpeedPerception, correctNormalized

PEARSON deltaTimePerception~correctNormalized			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.26199932	-0.0183263	-0.1423184	0.02471

PEARSON abs(deltaTimePerception)~correctNormalized			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.1353348	0.1132671	-0.011207	0.8603

PEARSON correctNormalized~reportedSpeedPerception			
95% CI	cor	p	
0.1057371	0.09529		

SPEARMAN deltaTimePerception~reportedSpeedPerception		
rho	p	
-0.183665	0.003633	

SPEARMAN abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedSpeedPerception		
rho	p	
0.0393982	0.536	

SPEARMAN correctNormalized~reportedSpeedPerception		
rho	p	
0.1057371	0.09529	

Confounding effects of fatigue

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), reportedSpeedPerception, correctNormalized, reportedFatigue

ANOVA correctNormalized~reportedFatigue		
F	p	
2.887	0.0231	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~reportedFatigue		
F	p	
2.073	0.085	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedFatigue		
F	p	
0.888	0.472	

TUKEY HSD

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	diff	lwr	upr	p adj
2-1	0.047397227	-0.0080436	0.1028381	0.1330884
3-1	0.056640878	-0.0008795	0.11416131	0.0559042
4-1	0.062360725	-0.0006705	0.12539201	0.0540487
5-1	0.093037448	-0.0111137	0.19718861	0.1045597
3-2	0.009243651	-0.0393846	0.0578719	0.9850335
4-2	0.014963498	-0.0400733	0.0700003	0.9450513
5-2	0.045640221	-0.0538765	0.14515701	0.7157039
4-3	0.005719847	-0.0514112	0.0628509	0.9987370
5-3	0.036396570	-0.0642935	0.13708661	0.8581603
5-4	0.030676723	-0.0732599	0.1346134	0.9270452

	diff	lwr	upr	p adj
2-1	-0.0730884	-0.2041964	0.0580196	0.5426384
3-1	0.0196387	-0.1167852	0.15606261	0.9948021
4-1	-0.0866973	-0.2357552	0.06236061	0.4997792
5-1	-0.1071618	-0.3534612	0.1391376	0.7538508
3-2	0.0927271	-0.0227409	0.2081952	0.1805511
4-2	-0.0136088	-0.1437613	0.1165436	0.9985020
5-2	-0.0340733	-0.2694131	0.20126631	0.9946857
4-3	-0.106336	-0.2418419	0.02916981	0.1999197
5-3	-0.1268005	-0.3651426	0.1115416	0.5880884
5-4	-0.0204644	-0.2662565	0.2253276	0.9993891

Spearman correctNormalized~reportedFatigue		
	rho	p
	0.184152	0.003476

Spearman deltaTimePerception~reportedFatigue		
	rho	p
	-0.0330207	0.6041

Spearman abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedFatigue		
	rho	p
	0.0187781	0.7681

Spearman reportedSpeedPerception~reportedFatigue		
	rho	p
	0.2558575	4.249e-05

Confounding effects of trial index

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), correctNormalized, trialIndex

Pearson correctNormalized~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
0.2260842	0.4458254	0.3405976	3.306e-08

Pearson deltaTimePerception~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.1412653	0.1072945	-0.0172515	0.7865

Pearson abs(deltaTimePerception)~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0892507	0.1590740	0.03545891	0.5776